

Innovative eScience Technologies (eTEC 2020)

Guidelines for Application Pre-Proposal

GENERAL

Please refer to the Call for Proposals "Innovative eScience Technologies (eTEC 2020)" for the Terms and Conditions of this granting scheme. The call text is available at www.esciencecenter.nl.

The correct Application Form should be used. This form can be downloaded from www.esciencecenter.nl. Proposals must be submitted using the ISAAC submission system: www.isaac.nwo.nl (see below for details).

The pre-proposal should be written in English. The layout of the proposal should facilitate easy reading. A minimum font size of 10 pts is advised.

REGISTRATION FORM (BASIC DATA)

1. Details of the applicant(s)

Please provide details for all applicants; complete all boxes as requested in the form. You can include as many co-applicants as needed. The principal investigator (PI) is the contact person for correspondence.

In case the PI's primary expertise is ICT Science (i.e.: not a Domain Science / Research Discipline as mentioned in Section 1.2 of the call text), it is *required to include at least one* co-applicant and team member (see Section 4. 'Composition of the Research Team') from the primary Domain Science / Research Discipline of focus.

2a. Title of the proposal

Please provide a short but specific title for the research for which funding is being requested. The title entered here must be the same as in the project information screen of the ISAAC submission system.

2b. Keywords

Provide up to 6 keywords most representative of the proposed research.

2c. Project duration

Indicate the expected duration of the project in months. Typical projects last 3 years; a duration of 2.5 to 3.5 years is allowed.

2d. Abstract (summary in English)

Provide a summary of the proposal in English, using no more than 200 words.

2e. Classification

Indicate the Technical Research Direction the proposed work *mainly* belongs to. In case the research fits more than one of the named Technical Research Directions, please select the most appropriate one. In case your research does not exactly match one of the options, but you are of the opinion that your project idea still fits well within the aims and scope of the call, please direct your questions to the contact persons mentioned below.

Please use exactly one of the tick boxes to select one of the following Technical Research Directions:

- Tools for Data Quality, Integration and Cleaning
- Virtual Research Environments: Infrastructure for '1000' Experiments
- Platforms for Big & Complex Spatial Data
- Green Computing: Energy Efficiency in Research Computing

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3. Total funding requested

State the amount of cash funding requested, as well as the requested in-kind contribution from the eScience Center. Any additional local or external contributions (e.g. for local personnel, equipment, etcetera) should not be included in this amount.

4. Composition of the Research Team

List all the team members who will have a substantial and verifiable contribution to the proposed work. Also include the projected eScience RSEs. For all team members indicate their period and percentage of involvement; for eScience RSEs indicate the requested PYR. Please use the table in the application form.

5. Recent achievements, results, and impact (max. 1 page)

Please list a maximum of 10 key results, achievements, or forms of impact in the last 5 years, each either realised by the research team as a whole, by the PI, or by individual team members. This section should provide all relevant information for the independent Assessment Committee to be able to judge the quality of the research team, its members, and each members' importance to the research project.

RESEARCH PROPOSAL (MAX. 1700 WORDS IN TOTAL FOR SECTIONS 6 AND 7)

6. Description of the proposed research (+/- 1400 words)

The layout of the pre-proposal should facilitate easy reading. **For sections 6 and 7 combined no more than 1700 words may be used**, including text below figures, excluding literature references. The proposal should include:

- a. **Science: Background, research questions, approach, and innovation**, incl.:
 - the domain problem(s) from the selected Research Discipline for which innovative eScience technologies and software will be researched and developed;
 - the specific use case(s) from the selected Research Discipline;
 - the technology-oriented approach to tackle the described domain problem(s);
 - the associated technology-oriented research questions, if any;
 - the expected impact;
 - the relation of the proposed approach, solution, outcomes, and deliverables with (existing) state-of-the-art technological developments.
- b. **eScience: Technologies, methods, and expected impact**, incl.:
 - the key challenges of the selected Technical Research Direction (see 2e above) in relation to the selected Research Discipline and use case(s);
 - the eScience tools and methodologies to be developed, applied (re-used), integrated, or extended;
 - how the developed or applied eScience technologies contribute to the selected use case(s) and to the selected Research Discipline as a whole.
- c. **Re-use, sustainability, dissemination, and collaborations**, incl.:
 - how the proposed technological solutions will find use beyond the proposed work itself, after finalization of the project, and preferably also across disciplines;
 - how maintenance and sustainability of project results will be secured and managed;
 - how the project will serve as a stepping stone to building further collaborations, in science, industry, or both;
 - the efforts made to promote the results of the project (publications, demonstrations, workshops, training, etcetera).

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d. Data management

- If data is collected or generated during the research that has potential for re-use, please specify how this data will be stored and shared during and after the project.
- Specify what facilities and expertise are expected to be needed for data storage, and whether these are available to you.

e. Software sustainability

- If software developed during the project is applicable for re-use, please indicate how the software will be licensed and be made available to third parties, and what effort will be needed to ensure re-usability.
- Indicate the size of the community able to re-use the software developed within the project
- Indicate what expertise is needed in order to make the software re-usable, and what contributions you would need from the eScience Center in making the software re-usable.

f. Use of Dutch National e-Infrastructure

Indicate the project's (national) e-Infrastructure needs, in terms of compute hours, data storage capacity, lightpath connectivity, or otherwise. A 'use-or-explain' policy is applied, meaning that:

- projects *without* e-Infrastructure needs are asked to give a brief explanation;
- projects with clear e-Infrastructure needs are expected to select the hardware resources and services as part of the Dutch National e-Infrastructure as first option, and to indicate the expected extent of use (see Appendix D in the Call for Proposals);
- projects with clear e-Infrastructure needs that aim to use international (e.g. PRACE, EUDAT, EGI, XSEDE, etcetera) or commercial (e.g. web, cloud, etcetera) hardware and services instead are required to give a brief explanation (see Appendix D in the Call for Proposals).

The use of the Dutch National e-Infrastructure is not a requirement, nor is it a formal review criterion. However, in all cases in which the Dutch National e-Infrastructure is not used, a justification should be provided.

g. Environmental impact

Similar to many other human endeavors, scientific research impacts the environment. The eScience Center is committed to minimizing the environmental impact of the projects it awards and participates in. Please indicate how your project will contribute, following the three R's:

- **Reduce**, e.g.:
 - by optimizing applied research software to use less (compute) resources;
 - by traveling less and using more online videoconferencing tools instead.
- **Re-use**, e.g.:
 - by contributing to existing software tools, engaging in existing communities;
 - by using trained models instead of re-training.
- **Recycle**, e.g.:
 - by using software libraries and data sets developed and generated elsewhere;
 - by making sure that materials (hardware, lab equipment, etcetera) will be recycled and/or are the result of recycling.

The environmental impact section is not part of the formal review procedure. The eScience Center, however, strongly encourages applicants to consider the above examples and/or to propose alternative ways to minimize, or compensate and account for, environmental impact.

7. Workplan and Timetable (+/- 300 words)

Provide a detailed workplan (e.g. in work packages) and a (provisional) timetable. In particular, specify clearly the role of the eScience RSE(s), and the expected involvement in terms of duration (specify preferred start-date and end-date) and percentage of participation (full-time or part-time).

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8. Deliverables

Provide a detailed list of the expected deliverables of the project, e.g. incl. publications, software releases, demonstrators, (video) presentations, etcetera.

9. References

List of references cited in the pre-proposal, with full bibliographic details.

ADMINISTRATIVE DETAILS

10. Requested funding within the total budget

The available budget for a single project is a maximum k€ 253 in cash contribution, and a minimum 2.5 PYR in-kind contribution in the form of eScience RSEs employed by the eScience Center.

Please specify costs for personnel, equipment, software, and travel using the layout as given in the application form. Personnel costs for Postdocs are specified in Table 1 below according to the most recent VSNU agreement. In case more than 2.5 PYR in-kind eScience Center support is requested, the in cash budget for a) + b) is lowered by €8,500 per 0.1 PYR.

Requested equipment and software must be intended for use in the project described in the proposal. Both the relationship with the project and the necessity of the equipment must be justified. Equipment and software with a purchase price of less than €5,000 forms part of the research institute's standard infrastructure and is not eligible for funding. Travel expenses may not exceed a maximum of €10,000. Travel expenses of eScience Center personnel need not be specified. The necessity of any travel undertaken in connection with the project must be justified.

Table 1

Following the NWO-VSNU-agreement for the period 1 July 2019 – 1 July 2020, for postdocs the standard research personnel fees (excl. bench fees) in € for 1,0 FTE are as follows:

duration	Postdoc
1 year	€ 76.818
2 years	€ 155.373
3 years	€ 235.705

Benchfee

Also following the NWO-VSNU-agreement for the period 1 July 2019 – 1 July 2020, the bench fees for postdocs are €5.000 for each appointed temporary staff member.

Please be informed that the agreement is expected to change in July 2020. As a result, the above fees are indicative, and hold for the pre-proposal phase only. In the full proposal phase the most recent agreement will apply; it is expected that the above fees will have been raised somewhat by that time.

11. Software and data health checks

All information concerning the software and data health checks is included in the 2020 eTEC call text (see Section 3.1 and Appendix C). The requested information is not part of the review procedure in the pre-proposal phase. If the data and software are not yet available for inspection in the pre-proposal phase, the questions can be left unanswered. Note, however, that the software and data health checks do form an integral part of the review procedure in the full proposal phase. At that time, all questions must be answered in the proposal, or alternatives must be discussed with the eScience Center.

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12. Statements by the applicant

The eScience Center requires applicants to endorse the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (see www.eugdpr.org), the Code Openness Animal Experiments and the Biosecurity Code of Conduct (both available at www.knaw.nl) and act according to these. Applicants are asked to also endorse and follow the Netherlands eScience Center Policy towards Publishing, Licensing, and Intellectual Property (at: www.esciencecenter.nl). For alternative IP agreements, the eScience Center must be contacted before proposal submission.

PROPOSAL SUBMISSION

The pre-proposal should be submitted as a PDF file via the electronic application system ISAAC before **25 June 2020, 14:00 CET**. More information on the use of ISAAC is available at www.nwo.nl. The proposal must be submitted from the ISAAC account of the principal investigator.

For technical questions about the use of ISAAC, please contact the ISAAC helpdesk. Applicants are requested to read the ISAAC manual before consulting the helpdesk. The ISAAC helpdesk is available from Monday to Friday from 11.00 to 17.00 hours on +31 (0)20 346 7179. You can also send your questions by email to isaac.helpdesk@nwo.nl. You will receive a reply within two working days.

A list of possible referees/non-referees should be added to the ISAAC fact sheet. You can exclude a maximum of 3 referees.

In accordance with the NWO-VSNU agreement, applicants should inform their local institute of the proposal. A copy of the proposal should be sent to the scientific director or dean of your department or institute. By submitting a proposal, you state that you have informed your local institute and that you and your local institute accept the terms and conditions of this granting scheme.

MORE INFORMATION

For more information, please check www.esciencecenter.nl or contact:

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